

Lattice Properties of Alkali Hydrides and Deutrides using Interaction Potentials

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Values of Cohesive energy, atomisation energy, Grüneisen parameter, Anderson – Grüneisen parameter, Moelwyn – Hughes parameter, binding energy and dissociation energy of alkali hydrides and deutrides have been computed using three interaction potentials, namely, Born – Mayer, Hellmann and Wasastjerna, and using our own method of calculation. The results obtained have been compared with the experimental as well as available literature data. The present communication reveals that the Hellmann potential model is highly successful in predicting the lattice properties of alkali hydrides and deutrides both in crystalline and gaseous state.

VARIOUS forms of interaction potentials have been used by various workers¹⁻⁷ for the evaluation of lattice properties of ionic crystals and molecules. In the present paper, we have selected only three well-known potentials suggested by Born–Mayer⁸, Hellmann⁹ and Wasastjerna¹⁰. Using a recent method of evaluation suggested by Mathur and Singh¹¹ and Thakur¹², the lattice properties of alkali hydrides and deutrides were calculated and the results obtained were compared with the experimental values and available literature data.

The above mentioned interaction potential in crystalline state are

$$\phi(r) = -\frac{AZ_1Z_2e^2}{r} + P_1 \exp\left(-\frac{r}{\lambda_1}\right) \quad (1)$$

Born–Mayer

$$\phi(r) = -\frac{AZ_1Z_2e^2}{r} + \frac{P_2}{r} \exp(-\lambda_2 r) \quad (2)$$

Hellmann

$$\phi(r) = -\frac{AZ_1Z_2e^2}{r} + P_3 r^\gamma \exp(-\lambda_3 r) \quad (3)$$

Wasastjerna

where, A is Madelung constant, P_1 and λ_1 are potential parameters in crystalline state and Z_1e and Z_2e are the charges on the ions, $\phi(r)$ is the potential energy of an ion-pair interaction with each other and with the rest of lattice and r is the interionic distance. In the gaseous state, the above mentioned potentials models can be written as

$$U(r) = -\frac{Z_1Z_2e^2}{r} + P'_1 \exp\left(-\frac{r}{\lambda'_1}\right) \quad (4)$$

$$U(r) = -\frac{Z_1Z_2e^2}{r} + \frac{P'_2}{r} \exp(-\lambda'_2 r) \quad (5)$$

$$U(r) = -\frac{Z_1Z_2e^2}{r} + P'_3 r^\gamma \exp(-\lambda'_3 r) \quad (6)$$

where, P'_i and λ'_i are potential parameters in gaseous states. For convenience, the parameters in the crystalline and the gaseous states are related as

$$P = MP'_i \text{ and } \lambda_i = \lambda'_i \quad (7)$$

where M is the coordination number which is 6 for f.c.c. lattice.

Method of calculation: The usual method of calculating the potential parameters suggested by Kachhava and Saxena and reviewed by Pandey can not be applied for crystals in general due to lack of available literature data. In the present paper we have used a recent method of calculation suggested by Thakur⁴. The utility of the method is based on the use of Moelwyn–Hughes parameter which requires the knowledge of crystal structure and values of interionic distances, the latter being known to a high degree of accuracy.

Potential parameters P and λ have been computed using the following conditions of stability and compressibility,

$$\phi'(r_0) = 0$$

$$\text{and } \phi''(r_0) = H/r_0^m$$

The values of H and m used have been taken from Thakur⁴, assuming that the values are the same for alkali halides, hydrides and deutrides having the same crystal structure.

Cohesive energy (W) and atomisation energy (E_a): Cohesive energy (W) and atomisation energy (E_a) are given by the relations,

$$W = -N[\phi(r_0) + E_0] \quad (8)$$

$$E_a = W + E - I \quad (9)$$

where, N is Avogadro number and E_0 is the zero-point energy obtained by the relation,

$$E_0 = \frac{9}{8} Nk\theta \quad (10)$$

where, k is Boltzmann's constant, θ is the Debye temperature where E is electron affinity¹⁹, I is ionisation potential²⁰ and r_0 is interionic distance^{19,20}. The computed values of W and E_a are listed in Table 1 together with the experimental values¹⁹ and available literature data¹⁴.

Grüneisen parameter (γ), Anderson—Grüneisen parameter (δ) and Moelwyn—Hughes parameters (C_1): Grüneisen parameter is given by the relation,

$$\gamma = -\frac{\gamma_0}{\sigma} \left[\frac{\phi''(r_0)}{\phi'(r_0)} \right] \quad (11)$$

where primes refer to the second and third derivatives of $\phi(r)$, respectively. Anderson—Grüneisen parameter is obtained by using Chang relation¹⁵ connecting r and δ . Moelwyn—Hughes parameter (C_1) is given by

$$C_1 = 1 - \frac{\beta_0}{27K_1} \phi'''(r_0)$$

where, β_0 is compressibility and K_1 is the crystal structure parameter, which is 2 for f.c.c. lattice and 1.54 for b.c.c. lattice. The computed values of r , δ and C_1 are listed in Table 2 together with the calculated values¹⁶ available in literature.

Binding energy (D_1) and dissociation energy (D_e): Binding energy per molecule is related to the potential function $U(r)$ in gaseous state by

$$D_1 = -NU(re) \quad (13)$$

TABLE 1—CALCULATED VALUES OF COHESIVE ENERGY (W) AND ATOMISATION ENERGY (E_a) FOR ALKALI HYDRIDE AND DEUTRIDE CRYSTALS ACCORDING TO POTENTIALS (1), (2) AND (3)

Crystal	W (kJ mol ⁻¹)				E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)			
	Exptl.	Pot. (1)	Pot. (2)	Pot. (3)	Exptl.	Pot. (1)	Pot. (2)	Pot. (3)
LiH	905.8	924.0	911.4	1 177.3	469.0	478.5	465.8	731.7
LiD	—	929.1	916.1	1 185.0	—	479.3	466.3	735.9
NaH	810.9	832.2	828.5	983.9	384.1	411.3	407.6	563.0
NaD	—	836.7	833.0	989.6	—	411.6	407.9	564.5
KH	714.2	747.6	746.5	899.6	368.2	403.7	402.6	495.7
KD	—	752.0	750.9	844.7	—	403.9	402.8	496.6
RbH	689.9	717.1	716.4	793.4	384.9	398.6	397.9	464.9
CsH	655.2	687.4	686.9	750.6	343.1	365.5	366.1	449.8
Av. % Dev.		3.6	3.2	19.7		6.5	5.9	16.9

TABLE 2—CALCULATED VALUES OF GRÜNEISEN PARAMETER (γ), ANDERSON—GRÜNEISEN PARAMETER (δ) AND MOELWYN—HUGHES PARAMETER (C_1) FOR ALKALI HYDRIDE AND DEUTRIDE CRYSTALS ACCORDING TO POTENTIALS (1), (2) AND (3)

Crystal	r				δ				C_1			
	Pot. (1)	Pot. (2)	Pot. (3)	Calcd.*	Pot. (1)	Pot. (2)	Pot. (3)	Calcd.*	Pot. (1)	Pot. (2)	Pot. (3)	Calcd.*
LiH	1.363	1.079	0.325	1.947	2.727	2.158	0.651	3.894	3.727	3.158	1.651	4.894
LiD	1.361	1.073	0.309	1.943	2.722	2.147	0.619	3.886	3.722	3.147	1.619	4.886
NaH	1.573	1.401	0.998	2.009	3.146	2.802	1.996	4.198	4.146	3.802	2.996	5.198
NaD	1.568	1.395	0.989	2.097	3.137	2.791	1.978	4.194	4.136	3.971	2.978	5.194
KH	1.966	1.856	1.623	2.248	3.932	3.712	3.247	4.496	4.932	4.712	4.247	5.496
KD	1.959	1.848	1.614	2.246	3.919	3.697	3.228	4.492	4.919	4.697	4.228	5.492
RbH	2.169	2.076	1.884	2.307	4.939	4.151	3.768	4.614	5.939	5.151	4.768	5.614
CsH	2.407	2.327	2.168	2.367	4.815	4.654	4.336	4.734	5.815	5.654	5.336	5.734

* Ref. 16.

TABLE 3—CALCULATED VALUES OF BINDING ENERGY (D_1) AND DISSOCIATION ENERGY (D_e) FOR ALKALI HYDRIDE AND DEUTRIDE MOLECULES ACCORDING TO POTENTIALS (1), (2) AND (3)

Crystal	D_1 (kcal mol ⁻¹)				D_e (kcal mol ⁻¹)			
	Exptl.	Pot. (1)	Pot. (2)	Pot. (3)	Exptl.	Pot. (1)	Pot. (2)	Pot. (3)
LiH	165.1	151.5	179.2	140.4	58.0	45.0	72.7	33.9
LiD	—	151.4	179.6	140.7	—	43.9	72.1	33.2
NaH	150.3	141.3	148.8	134.2	47.0	40.7	48.2	33.6
NaD	—	141.3	149.1	134.3	—	39.7	47.5	32.7
KH	127.2	127.7	121.1	124.7	42.9	45.5	38.9	42.5
KD	—	127.8	121.6	124.7	43.3	44.6	38.4	41.5
RbH	119.6	123.4	110.3	121.0	39.0	44.9	31.8	42.5
CsH	115.7	119.1	97.9	117.2	41.0	47.2	26.0	45.3
Av. % Dev.		4.15	4.06	6.08		11.03	13.3	15.8

where, r_e is the equilibrium internuclear distance²¹ of the crystals in gaseous state, and dissociation energy (D_e) may be evaluated by the relation,

$$D_e = D_1 + E - I \quad (14)$$

The computed values of D_1 and D_e are listed in Table 3 with experimental values of Varshni and Shukla¹⁷ and Gaydon¹⁸.

Discussion

It is evident from Tables 1–3 that there is a fair agreement between the computed and experimental values of W , E_a , D_1 and D_e . γ , δ and C_1 when computed on Wasastjerna model gives the least values in comparison to values obtained by Born–Mayer and Hellmann model. It is also remarkable that the values of W and D_1 for hydrides are less than the corresponding values for deuterides, showing that the forces which bind the crystals and molecules together are greater in case of deuterides than the corresponding hydrides. It is also interesting to note that among the three potential models used, Hellmann model gives the least average percentage deviation when computed values are compared with the experimental values and calculated values available in literature, thus rendering the model the most suitable for the evaluation of potential parameters.

A relation between Anderson–Grüneisen parameter (δ) and Moelwyn–Hughes parameter (C_1): Anderson–Grüneisen parameter is connected with Moelwyn–Hughes parameter, by the relation,

$$C_1 = 1 + \delta \quad (15)$$

The validity of this relation is apparent from results listed in Table 2. This relation was tested using various potential models for various ionic crystals and was found correct.

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